

Supplementary data- Urea-PAGE gels: DNA Ligases Discriminate Between Natural and Non-Natural Base Pairs

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1. DNA Ligase activity of Bsp-Lig, Pmar-LigP, Ame-Lig, Pmar-LigW, Ac42-Lig and P10VF-Lig with hachimoji substrates containing consecutive AEGIS bases.

DNA Ligase activity of Bsp-Lig, Pmar-LigP, Ame-Lig, Pmar-LigW, Ac42-Lig and P10VF-Lig with hachimoji substrates. 'Nat' represents substrates with only natural base pairs. '3'SB' represents substrates with S:B bases on the 3' end of the nick. '5'SB' represents substrates with S:B base pairs on the 5' end of the nick. 'BSB' represents substrates with S:B base pairs on both ends of the nick. '3'PZ' represents substrates with P:Z bases on the 3' end of the nick. '5'PZ' represents substrates with P:Z base pairs on the 5' end of the nick. 'BPZ' represents substrates with P:Z base pairs on both ends of the nick.

Assays were run with standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20 nM of protein. Samples were incubated at 25 °C for 30 minutes).

Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 3 of the main manuscript**.

2. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP, and Ac42-Lig with 'S' or 'pS' bases on the nick termini

'Natural' represents substrates with only natural base pairs. '3'SB' represents substrates with S:B bases on the 3' end of the nick. '5'SB' represents substrates with S:B base pairs on the 5' end of the nick. 'BSB' represents substrates with S:B base pairs on both ends of the nick. '3'pSB' represents substrates with pS:B bases on the 3' end of the nick. '5'pSB' represents substrates with pS:B base pairs on the 5' end of the nick. 'BpSB' ("both pS-B") represents substrates with pS:B base pairs on both ends of the nick. Assays were run with standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20 nM of protein). Samples were incubated at 25 °C for 30 minutes.

Double bands in the product region of the BSB substrate are from incomplete denaturation of the ligated product on the urea PAGE gel. Both bands are included as product during integration.

Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 3 of the main manuscript**.

3. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with hachimoji substrates containing individual AEGIS bases on each side of the nick.

'Natural nick' represents substrates with only natural base pairs. The first letter represents the unnatural base on the 3' end of the nick and the second letter represents the unnatural base on the 5' end, e.g. The 'P-S' substrate has a P on the 3' end and a S on the 5' end. Assays were run with standard conditions. (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20 nM of protein). Samples were incubated at 25 °C for 30 minutes.

Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 4 of the main manuscript**.

4. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with hachimoji substrates. In the presence of various crowding agents.

a) Assays run with standard conditions but addition of 10% crowding agent. 'Control' represents substrates with no crowding agent. '3350' represents substrates with PEG 3350. '6000' represents substrates with PEG 6000. '8000' represents substrates with PEG 8000. 'Beta' represents substrates with Betaine. 'Gly' represents substrates with Glycerol. b) DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with hachimoji substrates run with standard conditions but was incubated at 15°C for 18 hr. Double bands in the product region of some gels are from incomplete denaturation of the ligated product on the urea PAGE gel. Both bands are included as product during integration.

Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 6 of the main manuscript**.

a)

b)

5. DNA Ligase activity with hachimoji substrates under “optimised” conditions

Optimised' conditions include 10% PEG3350, 15°C for 18 hr, molar excess of enzyme. a) Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig b) Bsp-Lig, Ame-Lig and P10VF-Lig

'Natural' represents substrates with only natural base pairs. 'BSB' represents substrates with S:B base pairs on both ends of the nick. 'BPZ' represents substrates with P:Z base pairs on both ends of the nick. From the single hachimoji substrates, the first letter represents the non-canonical base on the 3' end of the nick and the second letter represents the non-canonical base on the 5' end, e.g. The 'B-Z' substrate has a B on the 3' end and a Z on the 5' end.

Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 7 of the main manuscript**.

a)

b)

6. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with natural mismatched DNA substrates

'Natural' represents substrates with no mismatches. '3' A-C' represents a mismatch of A-C on the 3' end of the nick. '3' A-G' represents a mismatch of A-G on the 3' end of the nick. '5' C-A' represents a mismatch of C-A on the 5' end of the nick. '5' G-A' represents a mismatch of G-A on the 5' end of the nick. a) standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes). b) optimised conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1.9 μM protein. Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 8**.

a)

7. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with hachimoji mismatched DNA substrates on the nicked DNA strand

'Natural' represents substrates with no mismatches. '5'B' represents a B base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. '5'pS' represents a pS base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. '5'P' represents a P base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. '5'Z' represents a Z base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. '3'B' represents a B base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end of the nick. '3'pS' represents a pS base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end of the nick. '3'P' represents a P base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end of the nick. a) standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes). b) optimised conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1.9 μM protein. Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 9**.

a)

b)

8. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with hachimoji mismatched DNA substrates on the complement DNA strand

'Natural' represents substrates with no mismatches. '3'B' represents a B base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end of the nick. '3'S' represents a S base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end of the nick. '3'P' represents a P base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end of the nick. '3'Z' represents a Z base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end of the nick. '5'B' represents a B base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. '5'S' represents a S base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. '5'P' represents a P base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. '5'Z' represents a Z base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end of the nick. a) standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes). b) optimised conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1.9 μM protein. Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 9** of the main manuscript.

a)

b)

9. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with hachimoji mismatched DNA substrates on both 3' and 5' of the nicked DNA strand

'Natural' represents substrates with no mismatches. The first letter represents the unnatural base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end and the second letter represents the unnatural base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end, e.g. The 'P-pS' substrate has a P on the 3' end and a pS on the 5' end. a) standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes). The second sets have optimised conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1.9 μM protein. Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 10**

a)

b)

10. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with hachimoji mismatched DNA substrates on both 3' and 5' of the complement DNA strand.

'Natural' represents substrates with no mismatches. The first letter represents the unnatural base replacing the correct natural base on the 3' end and the second letter represents the unnatural base replacing the correct natural base on the 5' end, e.g. The 'P-pS' substrate has a P on the 3' end and a pS on the 5' end. a) standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes). b) optimised conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1.9 μM protein. Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 10**

11. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with multiple mismatched hachimoji bases on either side of the break

'Natural' represents substrates with no mismatches. '5' Nick BSS' represents BSS bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 5' end of the nicked strand. '3' Nick SBBC' represents SBBC bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 3' end of the nicked strand. '5' Nick ZZZ' represents ZZZ bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 5' end of the nicked strand. '3' Nick PPP' represents PPP bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 3' end of the nicked strand. '5' Comp BBS' represents BBS bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 5' end of the complement strand. '3' Comp SSB' represents SSB bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 3' end of the complement strand. '5' Comp PPP' represents PPP bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 5' end of the complement strand. '3' Nick ZZZ' represents ZZZ bases replacing the correct natural bases on the 3' end of the complement strand. a) standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes). b) optimised conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1.9 μM protein. Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 11**

a)

b)

12. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP and Ac42-Lig with multiple mismatched hachimoji bases on both sides of the break

'Nick SSBC-BBS' represents mismatches of SSBC and BBS on the 3' and 5' end of the nicked strand respectively. 'Nick SSBC-ZZZ' represents mismatches of SSBC and ZZZ on the 3' and 5' end of the nicked strand respectively. 'Nick PPP-BBS' represents mismatches of PPP and BBS on the 3' and 5' end of the nicked strand respectively. 'Nick PPP-ZZZ' represents mismatches of PPP and ZZZ on the 3' and 5' end of the nicked strand respectively. 'Comp BBS-GSSB' represents mismatches of BBS and GSSB on the 3' and 5' end of the complement strand respectively. 'Comp PPP-ZZZ' represents mismatches of PPP and ZZZ on the 3' and 5' end of the complement strand respectively. a) standard conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes). b) optimised conditions (80 nM double stranded DNA oligonucleotides, 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1.9 μM protein. Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Samples were incubated at 15°C for 1440 minutes). Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Figure 11**.

a)

b)

13. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP with natural nicked DNA for steady-state kinetic calculations.

DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP with natural nicked DNA for steady-state kinetic calculations. Numbers atop the gels represent time points in seconds. DNA concentration denoted on the left. Conditions included 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 10 nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C. Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Supplementary 5**.

14. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP with 3' acceptor S:B DNA for steady-state kinetic calculations.

Numbers atop the gels represent time points in seconds. DNA concentration denoted on the left. Conditions included 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20 nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C. Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Supplementary 5**

15. DNA Ligase activity of Pmar-LigP with 3' acceptor P:Z DNA for steady-state kinetic calculations.

Numbers atop the gels represent time points in seconds. DNA concentration denoted on the left. Conditions included 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20 nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C. Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Supplementary 5**

16. DNA Ligase activity of Ac42-Lig with natural nicked DNA for steady-state kinetic calculations

Numbers atop the gels represent time points in seconds. DNA concentration denoted on the left. Conditions included 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg²⁺, 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 1 nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C. Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Supplementary 5**

17. DNA Ligase activity of Ac42-Lig with 3' acceptor S:B DNA for steady-state kinetic calculations

Numbers atop the gels represent time points in seconds. DNA concentration denoted on the left. Conditions included 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg^{2+} , 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20 nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C. Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Supplementary 5**

18. DNA Ligase activity of Ac42-Lig with 3' acceptor P:Z DNA for steady-state kinetic calculations

Numbers atop the gels represent time points in seconds. DNA concentration denoted on the left. Conditions included 1 mM ATP, 10 mM Mg^{2+} , 50 mM TRIS pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT and 20 nM protein. Samples were incubated at 25°C. Quantified relative ligation percentages are presented in **Supplementary 5**

